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Project Title:

Thermal and energy Management for INcreased Driving range of an Electric minibus including improved user-centric Design and thermal comfort

Acronym: **MINDED**

Grant Agreement No.: **101138202**

Topic: **User-centric design and operation of EV for optimized energy efficiency (2ZERO Partnership)**

Topic identifier: **HORIZON-CL5-2023-D5-01-01**

Type of action: **Innovation Action (IA)**

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Written by	Thomas BÄUML (AIT)	2024-03-11
Checked by	Irina MARIC (AIT) Ivana VALENTIĆ (RT)	2024-03-13 2024-03-21
Approved by	Dragan ŠIMIĆ (AIT)	2024-03-21
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D7.1: Project handbook (PU)

Publishable Executive Summary

In order to ensure the quality of the outcomes of the MINDED project, deliverable D7.1 undertakes the crucial task of formulating a comprehensive Project handbook. This document encompasses the formulation of procedures and standards, the identification and assignment of responsibilities to uphold these benchmarks, and the implementation of ample monitoring and control mechanisms.

Thus, D7.1 emerges as the pivotal document outlining the quality assurance protocols essential for the MINDED project's success. Its overall objective is to safeguard that all outputs and deliverables generated within the project are at a high-quality standard.

The project handbook, which should govern all partners and consortiums actions, must be accepted by the MINDED consortium. Once accepted, D7.1 becomes an official project document which is open for review processes through the entire MINDED project duration (e.g. during each general assembly meeting the procedures will be reviewed and updated if required).

As the project MINDED is closely related to the project EMPOWER and the coordination for both projects is in the hands of the same persons at AIT, synergies between the projects are exploited to reduce project management efforts. Therefore, the project handbook of MINDED is very similar to the project handbook of EMPOWER.

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Abbreviations and Nomenclature

Table 1: List of Abbreviations and Nomenclature

Symbol or Shortname	Description
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
GA	General Assembly
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IR	Infrared Radiation
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote

1 Introduction

1.1 The MINDED project

The objective of MINDED is to deliver a battery-electric, zero-emission IVECO eDaily minibus with a 20 % improved range at 0 °C. This objective is reached through the highly efficient heating system for the driver and passengers based on infrared (IR) heating panels, controlled by optimal thermal and energy management strategy, and supported by an innovative human-machine interface (HMI), and an optimised air conditioning system in heat pump mode, using innovative oil-free centrifugal e-compressor with gas bearing technology. The performance of the implemented heating system will be demonstrated on a chassis dynamometer at 0 °C ambient temperature at TRL 7, while the air conditioning system performance in heat pump mode will be demonstrated on the ThermoLab testbed under various operating conditions at TRL 6. The targeted TRLs in MINDED are fully consistent with the call's requirement to achieve at least TRL 6 by the end of the project.

To further improve the performance of the IVECO eDaily minibus, an overall predictive thermal and energy management strategy will be demonstrated in the Digital Twin Model of the entire vehicle. The model considers the vehicle's powertrain, the implemented infrared heating and air conditioning systems, and a prediction of the driving behaviour based on artificial intelligence (AI) and Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) sensors.

The ambition of MINDED involves the development, implementation, and demonstration of technologies at TRL 6-7, with 20 % improved real-world range at 0 °C compared to the baseline battery-electric IVECO eDaily minibus. MINDED developments will yield a cost reduction of at least 5 % at the vehicle level, while increasing the performance and reliability, and the development time reduction by 30 % through digital twin and AI deployment.

1.2 Scope of the project handbook

The aim of deliverable D7.1 is to assure that the objectives of the project MINDED are met and that the results and deliverables of the project are of high quality, fulfilling the specifications set in the description of the work and the grant agreement. Hence D7.1 is the document defining the quality assurance procedures for the MINDED project. The document is shared with the whole consortium and serves as the basis for all project related communication and quality related issues. Furthermore, the MINDED project handbook is a dynamic document that is continually edited and updated e.g. during each general assembly meeting.

The project handbook encompasses the description of the quality assurance procedures as well as document templates and is addressed to the project partners for the successful development of the EMPOWER project, and also to the European Commission evaluators for their evaluation of the project. Hence the project handbook will guide all consortium partners, which are responsible for preparing and amending deliverables (e.g. WP leader, Task leader), the steering committee, the project and quality coordinator (which is responsible for reviewing completed or updated parts of the project handbook and to carry out its disclaiming of liability) and any responsible consortium partner for approving works to be done by third parties, in order to complete deliverables.

1.3 Reference to D9.1 of EMPOWER

As the project MINDED is closely related to the project EMPOWER and the coordination for both projects is in the hands of the same persons at the AIT, also similarities in the project management exist and synergies should be exploited, to reduce the project management efforts. Therefore, the project handbook of MINDED will be very similar to the project handbook of EMPOWER and whole text passages will be copied from D9.1 Project handbook of EMPOWER to D7.1 Project handbook of MINDED.

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2 Organisational management structure

2.1 General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA) is the decision-making body of the consortium. Decisions can refer to all administrative and technical questions of the project. The GA consists of at least one member of each consortium partner.

Table 2: Members of the General Assembly

General assembly										
AIT	IVECO	RT	TUD	UOZ	TUW	IDIADA	VIL	GAR	LT	ATC

2.2 Project Coordinator

AIT is acting as Project Coordinator (PC) for this Project. The PC is the legal entity acting as an intermediary between the consortium and the Funding Authority. The coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

2.3 Governing bodies and responsibilities

Quality Coordinator

AIT is acting also as Quality Coordinator (QC). The QC monitors the progress of the MINDED project and reports any significant deviations in terms of results, quality, timing, and resources spent to the consortium. Furthermore, the QC will supervise that all project outcomes (like material used in presentations, conferences, and workshops) will have the same high level of quality.

Work Package Leader

The Work Package (WP) Leaders are responsible for the achievement of the related WP task objectives. Their role is to coordinate all efforts of their related WP and to monitor the progress by checking status and task quality. The leading beneficiaries for each WP are defined in the GA and listed here as follows:

- **WP1** Vehicle platform data acquisition: **IVECO**
- **WP2** Heating system and thermal user comfort: **AIT**
- **WP3** HVAC unit, ECU, and HMI: **RT**
- **WP4** Digital twin model and operating strategy: **TUW**
- **WP5** Implementation, demonstration, and assessment on vehicle level: **IVECO**
- **WP6** Dissemination, communication, and exploitation: **AIT**
- **WP7** Project management: **AIT**

Task leaders

The role and responsibility of task leaders is similar to the WP leaders but at the Task level (e.g. monitoring and coordinating the technical progress of the task). The task leaders report to the WP leader. In case of arising issues, the WP leader discusses the issue with the task leader and comes up with the proposed solution.

3 Quality Assurance – Reporting

3.1 Internal regular progress reporting

To ensure the quality and compliance to the project schedule of the project, each partner is requested to report the technical status of their work in oral form to the plenary panel in the regular monthly online plenary meetings. Current issues and open points are discussed between the PC and the partners and solutions as well as further steps are defined.

3.2 Internal 12-month progress reporting

To ensure the financial progress of the project, each partner is requested to report their financial status in written form to the PC every 12 months. Therefore, an Excel template will be sent out by the PC, and the used personnel months and travel-, equipment-, other goods, works, and services- costs are reported. The PC will then provide an overview in the GA meeting and discuss about further steps to ensure, that the project is financially on the right track.

The template to report the financial status can be obtained from the project network storage repository ([MINDED\admin\02-templates](#)), see also Chapter 4.2 and 7.2.

3.3 Progress report to the EC

At the end of each Reporting Period, progress reports must be submitted to the EC. According to the Grant Agreement, delivery dates are Month 18 and Month 36. The reports need to include the technical and financial progress. Reports will be created by the coordinator with the support of all WP leaders.

To achieve a timely delivery of the reports to the EC, the following timeline shall be followed:

- 4 weeks before deadline: Coordinator requests contents from WP leaders by email
- Deadline: WP leaders receive feedback from respective Task leaders
- 2 weeks after deadline: WP leaders are providing report draft to Coordinator
- 3 weeks after deadline: Coordinator sends out feedback on report draft
- 4 weeks after deadline: Final report is submitted to Coordinator

4 Quality Assurance – Creation of Deliverables

4.1 Dissemination levels

In this project, Deliverables can fall under two different confidentiality levels:

- Sensitive: Only accessible for consortium members (including the Commission Services)
- Public

Each Deliverable has to be allocated to one Dissemination category. An overview of the respective Level ranking of each Deliverables can be found in Appendix A2.

4.2 Templates

The official templates for Deliverables can be obtained from the project network storage repository ([MINDED\admin\02-templates](#)), see also Chapter 7.2. These templates have to be used by all project partners and for all Deliverable Reports. Each document has to fulfill the file naming rules. The detailed rules are listed in Chapter 7.1.

4.3 Reviewing and Approval

To assure deliverables with good quality, the deliverable reports need to be reviewed and checked before submission. This review shall be done by the PC and previously appointed reviewers.

The following timeline shall be followed for the submission of deliverables:

- 6 weeks before deadline: Coordinator requests contents from WP leaders by email
- 4 weeks before deadline: Deliverable draft is sent to coordinator for initial check
- 3 weeks before deadline: Revised deliverable is sent to reviewer by the coordinator
- 1 weeks before deadline: Final version is submitted to coordinator

Reviewers will be nominated for each deliverable separately. The selection of reviewers needs to follow these fundamental guidelines:

- Not involved in document creation
- Not part of coordinator

5 External communications and publications

5.1 Logo

Figure 2 shows the official MINDED project logo. This logo has been approved by the GA during the Kick-off meeting of MINDED. On external and internal publications, the use of the official project logo is required. The project logo is located on the project network storage repository ([MINDED\admin\06-logo](#)).

Figure 1: The MINDED logo

Figure 2: The MINDED icon

5.2 Presentations

To ensure that presented contents are clearly connected to MINDED and to create a recognition factor of the project itself, the usage of the official project presentation template is required for all official project presentations. This is especially the case for external presentations of project contents. The template document can be found on the project network storage repository ([MINDED\admin\02-templates](#)).

5.3 Rules

On all project publications, the funding by the European Union needs to be acknowledged. This includes the usage of the MINDED project logo and the EU flag in sufficiently high resolution.

Figure 3 : Logo showing the funding of the European Union

For the acknowledgement itself, the following sentence is mandatory:

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Additionally, dissemination documents need to bear the following disclaimer:

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These paragraphs are already included in the official project templates. Removing or modifying these sections is not permitted.

5.4 Procedures

Before executing any formal publication or external communication, the PC needs to be informed in advance. The PC will finally confirm the content and visual appearance. To ensure an orderly procedure, the following deadlines shall be met:

- 6 weeks before submission: Giving notification to Coordinator
- 2 weeks before submission: Summarising feedback and approval from Project Consortium

The PC regards the publication or communication as authorised, if no objection from the Project Consortium was received within the feedback period.

However, the publishing party needs to receive a written confirmation of that approval before any material can be submitted or communicated.

6 Communication and meeting management

6.1 Communication

Standard working communication shall be done via phone or email.

Important communication and exchange of information (e.g. to provide information on the release of new deliverables or to notify the project partners about the availability of new information and events or to circulate meeting agendas, etc.) should be done via email to enable tracking and follow-up. Therefore, a mailing list for the partners is available and will be maintained and kept up to date by the PC to ensure that no one will be excluded from important information. All addresses of the project partners can be found on the project network storage ([MINDED\admin\05-contacts](#)). In this contact list, everyone can also decide in which of the three mailing lists (technical, financial, or marketing related) they want to be included. To enable the coordinator to maintain an overview of the entire project, the coordinator contacts shall be included in all technical and administrative e-mails in copy (cc:).

6.2 Monthly web meeting

Web meetings are a powerful tool for keeping frequently in touch with partners via MS Teams web conferences. Monthly web meetings are organized by the PC and take place on every last Wednesday of the month from 09:00 to 10:30 am. Regardless of these regular meetings, spontaneous web meetings with short notice are possible at any time in order to save resources (e.g. traveling budget and time).

For web meetings generally the same principles are valid as for physical meetings. This means, all required documents must be shared with the attendees before the meeting. This includes an agenda and a participant list.

6.3 Face-to-Face meeting

The main pillar for communication in the project will be the Face-to-Face meetings. In order to foster the personal exchange of project participants across all WPs, these meetings will be held on a regular basis.

Two types of meetings shall be held in the course of the project:

- General Assembly meetings
- WP specific technical meetings

The following target dates have been set for the GA meetings:

- | | | |
|-------|----------|-----------------------|
| • M1 | Jan 2024 | 1. GA Kick-Off |
| • M9 | Sep 2024 | 2. GA meeting |
| • M13 | Jan 2025 | 3. GA meeting |
| • M21 | Sep 2025 | 4. GA meeting |
| • M25 | Jan 2026 | 5. GA meeting |
| • M33 | Sep 2026 | 6. GA meeting |
| • M36 | Dec 2026 | 7. GA final |

At each meeting, the location and type (Face-to-Face or online) of the following meeting shall be discussed and decided by the GA.

6.4 Meeting minutes

For conserving all relevant information discussed about in Face-to-Face or online meetings, minutes have to be created and stored in the respective folder on the network storage repository ([MINDED\admin\04-](#)

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[meetings](#)). The template for the meeting minutes can be found on the project network storage repository ([MINDED\admin\02-templates](#)). Meeting minutes include the date, time, duration, and location of a meeting, together with a list of all participants and a summary of relevant topics, information, questions, answers, and open points.

7 Electronic data management

7.1 Document creation

To ensure compatibility and open access to all electronic project documents, common standards on data formats need to be defined. Electronic project documents shall be created using the Microsoft Office software suite or compatible products. The following data formats need to be used:

- Text documents: Microsoft Office Word Document .docx
- Presentations Microsoft Office PowerPoint Presentation .pptx
- Spreadsheets Microsoft Office Excel Workbook .xlsx

All documents shall use the English language.

In order to manage the created number of documents, common rules for file names need to be followed. File names need to comply with the following rule:

- **MINDED_Index_DocName_Date_Version_Partner.ext**

with the following meanings:

- Index Number of WP or deliverable e.g. WP1 or D1.4
- DocName Short name suitable for content identification e.g. KickOff
- Date Date of document creation e.g. 2024-03-12
- Version Version number e.g. V1.1
- Partner Acronym of document responsible partner e.g. AIT
- ext File extension e.g. pptx

7.2 Data transfer and storage

Presentations and general documents shall be transmitted using the project network storage. This system is administered and maintained by the PC. After an invitation by the PC, the storage location can be accessed via the following URL:

<https://aitonline.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/MINDED/Shared%20Documents/MINDED?csf=1&web=1&e=V0D51a>

This will lead to a folder structure as can be seen in Figure 4 consisting of a folder admin and another one called data.

Figure 4: Overview of the MINDED project network storage top folder

The admin folder contains the subfolders depicted in Figure 5, which contain the most important information

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about the project as contact lists, templates, contracts, meetings incl. minutes, etc.

Figure 5: Admin folder of the MINDED project network storage

The data folder includes subfolders of each workpackage. The respective WP folders then contain data and information of the WPs. Also, the deliverables can be found in the corresponding WP folder.

Figure 6: Data folder of the MINDED project network storage

8 Conclusions

Procedures and standards to be used in the MINDED project to guarantee the quality of the outcomes were formulated within D7.1. To ensure that the quality assurance is alive during the entire project duration, the definition of the responsibilities occurred in D7.1 for ensuring that the mentioned procedures and standards are followed according to their designation in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. Hence an evaluation and quality assurance framework has been accomplished. D7.1 provides the necessary measures and actions in case of deviations in order to ensure the high-quality level of the project, of all deliverables, of the entire documentation, and to ensure the full compliance with all contractually fixed requirements.

9 Acknowledgment

European Union's HORIZON EUROPE research and innovation programme

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Project Partners:

The author(s) would like to thank the partners in the project for their valuable comments on previous drafts and for performing the review.

Participant No*	Participant short name	Participant organisation name	Country
1 Coordinator	AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH	Austria
2	IVECO	IVECO S.p.A	Italy
3	RT	Rimac Technology	Croatia
4	TUDA	Technical University of Darmstadt	Germany
5	UOZ	University of Zagreb	Croatia
6	TUW	Technical University of Vienna	Austria
7	IDIADA	IDIADA Automotive Technology S.A.	Spain
8	VIL	Villinger GmbH	Austria
9	GAR	Garrett Motion Czech Republic s.r.o.	Czechia
10	LT	Lead Tech SRL	Italy
11	ATC	TU Wien Automotive Test Center GmbH	Austria

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D7.1: Project handbook (PU)

Appendix A1 – Reporting Templates

Financial Report

[MINDED\admin\02-templates\MINDED_template-financialReport.xlsx](#)

MINDED		Please fill in the part A, B, C and D (ONLY green cells):			(A) direct personnel costs			(B) subcontracting costs				(C) purchase costs				(D) internally invoiced goods and ser.	
AIT		Person Month	Total Hours	Personnel EUR	EUR	Justification	EUR	Justification	EUR	Justification	EUR	Justification	EUR	Justification	EUR	Justification	
Workpackage / Task		Total															
WP1	Vehicle platform data acquisition	Total		0	0.00												Only if you have additionally unit costs !
		Actual		0	0.00												
WP2	Heating system and thermal user comfort	Total		0	0.00												unit costs:
		Actual		0	0.00												
WP3	HVAC unit, ECU, and HMI	Total		0	0.00												
		Actual		0	0.00												
WP4	Digital twin model and operating strategy	Total		0	0.00												
		Actual		0	0.00												
WP5	Implementation, demonstration, and assessment on vehicle level	Total		0	0.00												
		Actual		0	0.00												
WP6	Dissemination, communication, and exploitation	Total		0	0.00												
		Actual		0	0.00												
WP7	Project management	Total		0	0.00												
		Actual		0	0.00												
TOTAL			0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR	
ACTUAL			0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR		0.00 EUR	

Slides Template

[MINDED\admin\02-templates\MINDED_template-slides_16x9.pptx](#)

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MINDED

<name> Meeting

WPX: <WP name>

Presenter:
<First Name> <LAST NAME> (<Company>)

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D7.1: Project handbook (PU)

- Text
 - Text
 - Text

- Text
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 - Text

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D7.1: Project handbook (PU)

Thank you!

Presenter:

<First Name> <LAST NAME> (<Company>)

13.03.2024

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4

Agenda Template

[MINDED\admin\02-templates\MINDED_template-agenda.docx](#)

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Grant Agreement No.: **101138202**

Name of Meeting: **<Meeting Name> – Agenda**

Topic: **User-centric design and operation of EV for optimized energy efficiency
(2ZERO Partnership)**

Topic identifier: **HORIZON-CL5-2023-D5-01-01**

Type of action: **Innovation Action (IA)**

Coordinator: **Dragan SIMIC (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH)
Thomas BÄUML (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH)**

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8	VIL	Villinger GmbH	Austria
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11	ATC	TU Wien Automotive Test Center GmbH	Austria

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Minutes Template

[MINDED\admin\02-templates\MINDED_template-meetingMinutes.docx](#)

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Name of Meeting: **<Meeting Name> – Minutes**

Topic: **User-centric design and operation of EV for optimized energy efficiency
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5	UOZ	University of Zagreb	Croatia
6	TUW	Technical University of Vienna	Austria
7	IDIADA	IDIADA Automotive Technology S.A.	Spain
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Meeting Info

Date	<Date>
Start time	<Start time>
End Time	<End time>
Meeting venue	<Meeting Venue>
Hosting partner	<Hosting Partner>

List of Participants

No.	First name	Family name	Institution (short name)
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			
8			

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Deliverable Template

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the European Union

Project Title:

**Thermal and energy Management for INcreased
Driving range of an Electric minibus including
improved user-centric Design and thermal comfort**

Acronym: **MINDED**

Grant Agreement No.: **101138202**

Topic: **User-centric design and operation of EV for optimized energy efficiency
(2ZERO Partnership)**

Topic identifier: **HORIZON-CL5-2023-D5-01-01**

Type of action: **Innovation Action (IA)**

Deliverable No.	<DX.Y>	
Deliverable Title	<Title>	
Deliverable Date	<YYYY-MM>	
Deliverable Type	<Report>	
Dissemination level	<Public/Sensitive>	
Written by	<Name SURNAME (AFFILIATION) > <Name SURNAME (AFFILIATION) >	<YYYY-MM-DD> <YYYY-MM-DD>
Checked by	<Name SURNAME (AFFILIATION) > <Name SURNAME (AFFILIATION) >	<YYYY-MM-DD> <YYYY-MM-DD>
Approved by	<WP Leader> <Name SURNAME (AFFILIATION) > <Name SURNAME (AFFILIATION)>	<YYYY-MM-DD> <YYYY-MM-DD>
Status	<Version X.Y> <Version Y.Z>	<YYYY-MM-DD> <YYYY-MM-DD>

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D7.1: Project handbook (PU)

Publishable Executive Summary

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Abbreviations and Nomenclature

Table 1: List of Abbreviations and Nomenclature

Symbol or Shortname	Description
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote

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D7.1: Project handbook (PU)

1 Introduction

Write in Times New Roman 11 font size.

Rising global CO₂ emissions and increasing temperatures show the crucial need for drastic decarbonisation of our economies and lifestyles. To transform Europe's mobility, energy and production systems, the European Union (EU) has approved the European Green Deal Action Plan [1] which has the ambition of moving the Union towards a resource-efficient, competitive, and inclusive economy, and achieving full carbon neutrality in economic sectors by 2050.

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2 Second Chapter

Text ...

Figure 1: Test figure

Text

Table 2: Sample Table

Text	Text

2.1 Sub-Chapter

Text

2.1.1 Sub-Sub-Chapter

Text

Sub-Sub-Sub-Chapter

Text

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3 Third Chapter

Text

3.1 Sub-Chapter

Text

3.1.1 Sub-Sub-Chapter

Text

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4 Conclusions

Text

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5 Bibliography

- [1] "Green Deal Action Plan," European Commission. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1596443911913&uri=CELEX:52019DC0640#document1>. [Accessed 30 03 2023].

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6 Acknowledgment

European Union's HORIZON EUROPE research and innovation programme

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Project Partners:

The author(s) would like to thank the partners in the project for their valuable comments on previous drafts and for performing the review.

Participant No*	Participant short name	Participant organisation name	Country
1 Coordinator	AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH	Austria
2	IVECO	IVECO S.p.A	Italy
3	RT	Rimac Technology	Croatia
4	TUDA	Technical University of Darmstadt	Germany
5	UOZ	University of Zagreb	Croatia
6	TUW	Technical University of Vienna	Austria
7	IDIADA	IDIADA Automotive Technology S.A.	Spain
8	VIL	Villinger GmbH	Austria
9	GAR	Garrett Motion Czech Republic s.r.o.	Czechia
10	LT	Lead Tech SRL	Italy
11	ATC	TU Wien Automotive Test Center GmbH	Austria

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Appendix A1 - Quality Assurance

The following questions should be answered by all reviewers (WP Leader, peer reviewer 1 and the technical coordinator) as part of the Quality Assurance Procedure. Questions answered with NO should be motivated. The author will then make an updated version of the Deliverable. When all reviewers have answered all questions with YES, only then the Deliverable can be submitted to the EC.

NOTE: This Quality Assurance part will be removed before publication.

Question	WP Leader	Peer reviewer 1	Technical Coordinator
	Name SURNAME	Name SURNAME	Name SURNAME
1. Do you accept this deliverable as it is?	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
2. Is the deliverable completely ready (or are any changes required)?	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
3. Does this deliverable correspond to the DoW?	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
4. Is the Deliverable in line with the MINDED objectives?	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
a. WP Objectives?	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
b. Task Objectives?	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
5. Is the technical quality sufficient?	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No

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Appendix A2 – Deliverables and Milestones

List of Deliverables

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	WP number	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due Date (in months)
D1.1	Vehicle specifications, use cases and test catalogue	1	IVECO	R	SEN	8
D2.1	Report on infrared heating panels and enhanced thermal cabin insulation	2	AIT	R	PU	9
D2.2	Report on thermal mannequin for comfort evaluation	2	IDIADA	R	SEN	18
D2.3	Report on operating strategy for optimized energy efficiency of the heating system	2	UOZ	R	PU	18
D3.1	Optimal HVAC system layout	3	GAR	R	PU	18
D3.2	Control strategy for the e-compressor	3	GAR	R	SEN	30
D3.3	ECU and, driver and passenger HMIs	3	AIT	DEM/R	PU	24
D4.1	Entire vehicle 1D digital twin model	4	AIT	Other/R	PU	33
D4.2	Report on driving behaviour and vehicle velocity prediction	4	TUDA	R	SEN	31
D4.3	Report on user-centric comfort control strategy	4	IDIADA	R	SEN	29
D4.4	Report on overall vehicle thermal and energy predictive management strategy	4	UOZ	R	PU	33
D5.1	Measurement results of initial vehicle identification	5	TUW	R	PU	6
D5.2	Minibus demonstrator with integrated components	5	AIT	DEM/R	PU	31
D5.3	Measurement results of demonstrator with integrated heating system	5	TUW	R	PU	16
D5.4	Measurement results of demonstrator with integrated predictive operating strategy	5	TUW	R	PU	33
D5.5	Measurement results of developed HVAC system	5	TUDA	R	PU	33

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D7.1: Project handbook (PU)

D5.6	Virtual minibus performance assessment and optimisation	5	UOZ	R	PU	36
D6.1	Dissemination, exploitation (including IPR) and communication plan	6	AIT	R	PU	6
D6.2	First revision of dissemination, exploitation (including IPR) and communication activities	6	LT	R	PU	18
D6.3	Final report on dissemination, exploitation (including IPR) and communication activities	6	LT	R	PU	36
D7.1	Project handbook	7	AIT	R	PU	3
D7.2	Data management plan	7	AIT	DMP	PU	6
D7.3	First revision of data management plan	7	AIT	DMP	PU	18
D7.4	Final version of data management plan	7	AIT	DMP	PU	36

List of Milestones

Milestone number	Milestone title	WP number	Lead beneficiary	Due Date (in months)	Means of verification
MS1	Dissemination strategy, communication- and data management plan established	WP6, WP7	6	Review and availability check of D6.1, D7.1, D7.2	MS1
MS2	Vehicle technical specification, test catalogue, use cases and initial identification finalised	WP1, WP5	8	Review and availability check of D1.1, D5.1	MS2
MS3	Vehicle heating system tested, and comfort analysis evaluated	WP2, WP5	16	Review and availability check of D2.1, D5.3	MS3
MS4	Operating strategy of the heating system established	WP2, WP3	18	Review and availability check of D2.2, D2.3, D3.1	MS4
MS5	Development of driver and passenger HMIs finalised	WP3	24	Review and availability check of D3.3	MS5
MS6	Integration of components and modules into the vehicle realised	WP3, WP4, WP5	31	Review and availability	MS6

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D7.1: Project handbook (PU)

				check of D3.2, D4.2, D5.2	
MS7	HVAC and vehicle heating testing finalised	WP4, WP5	33	Review and availability check of D4.1, D4.4, D5.4, D5.5	MS7
MS8	Innovation action of MINDED successfully implemented and finalised	WP5, WP6, WP7	36	Review and availability check of D5.6, D6.3, D7.4	MS8

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D7.1: Project handbook (PU)

Appendix A3 – Review Process

List of Reviewers

Deliverable Number	Lead beneficiary	Reviewer
D1.1	IVECO	TBD by GA
D2.1	AIT	TBD by GA
D2.2	IDIADA	TBD by GA
D2.3	UOZ	TBD by GA
D3.1	GAR	TBD by GA
D3.2	GAR	TBD by GA
D3.3	AIT	TBD by GA
D4.1	AIT	TBD by GA
D4.2	TUDA	TBD by GA
D4.3	IDIADA	TBD by GA
D4.4	UOZ	TBD by GA
D5.1	TUW	TBD by GA
D5.2	AIT	TBD by GA
D5.3	TUW	TBD by GA
D5.4	TUW	TBD by GA
D5.5	TUDA	TBD by GA
D5.6	UOZ	TBD by GA
D6.1	AIT	TBD by GA
D6.2	LT	TBD by GA
D6.3	LT	TBD by GA
D7.1	AIT	RT
D7.2	AIT	TBD by GA
D7.3	AIT	TBD by GA
D7.4	AIT	TBD by GA

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